

THE WELL-BEING OF AN HONORARY TEACHER AND THE LONG JOURNEY TO THE ADVANCEMENT OF THE PROFESSION

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Abstract

The study aims to discuss how the well-being of honorary teachers in Indonesia and how the long road to the sustainability of the profession. The research also focuses on strategic recommendations to improve the well-being and sustainability of the professions of honorary teachers. This research uses a method of literary research or library study. This method uses sources of information from a variety of relevant literature, such as journals, books, articles, and previous research reports, which are then analyzed comprehensively and systematically. The results of the research show that the journey to improve the well-being and sustainability of the professions of honorary teachers in Indonesia is still quite long and challenging. Honourable teachers often receive undue salaries and have not received adequate protection of employment rights. Although the government has made some efforts, such as the selection of government officials by employment agreement (PPPK), it still leaves many challenges and requirements to be met. Therefore, strategic recommendations that can be implemented include raising honorary teacher salaries, protecting employment rights, providing special appointment routes, ining training and professional development, raising education budgets, as well as enforcing national standards of education and strengthening the role of teacher unions.

Keywords: Well-being, Honourable Teacher, Profession.

INTRODUCTION

Education has an important role in the formation of quality human resources and is the determinant of the development of a nation. Education and development of human resources (SDM) are two interrelated and fundamental elements in the process of building a nation (Nuryanto et al., 2023),(Susanto, 2024). Through education, individuals not only acquire the knowledge and skills needed to face the world of work, but also gain the formation of character and values that are essential to being part of a dynamic and thriving society. (Aris et al., 2023). Education, in this context, is not only about the transfer of knowledge, but also about building the capacity of individuals to realize their full potential. (Sitopu et al., 2024; Guna et al., 2024).

SDM development focuses on improving the quality of individuals and groups within an organization or society as a whole in order to optimize performance or a set goal (Pratikno et al., 2023). In the country context, the development of SDM is a prerequisite for innovation, economic growth, and social sustainability. (Ramly et al., 2024). Education plays a key role in the development of SDM by providing the basis for lifelong learning, skills improvement, and individual adaptation to technological and labour market changes. (Hairiyanto et al., 2024),(Ilham et al., 2024).

The role of education in SDM development is to create a competent workforce, advance innovation, promote equality and inclusion, and prepare future generations. With education, younger generations are prepared to face future challenges, including climate change, demographic change, and technological transformation. (Vlachoudi et al., 2023).

Thus, SDM education and development is a strong foundation for the development and progress of a nation. Through quality education, individuals can develop their potential, improve the quality of life, and make a significant contribution to society and the country. (Pratikno et al., 2022),(Sari et al., 2024).Therefore, investment in education and development of SDM must be a priority for every country that wants to sustainable and inclusive growth.

In this context, the teacher has a central role as the person responsible for the learning process. (Tubagus et al., 2023),(Nurhasnawati et al., 2024). Teachers have a crucial role in the learning process. They serve not only as information suppliers or teaching materials, but also as motivators, facilitators, and educators who guide students in the teaching learning process. (Aslan & Shiong, 2023). Quality of learning depends heavily on the competence and dedication of teachers in managing classrooms, identifying student learning needs, and implementing effective learning methods. Teachers play an important role in guiding and influencing learning quality. With skills, dedication, and adaptation to the changing world of education, teachers can help students reach their full potential. (Nurdiana et al., 2023; Sarmila et al., 2023).

In Indonesia, there are a large number of teachers with honorary status. Honorary teachers are referred to as teachers who do not have the status of Civil State Officer (PNS) or Government Officer with Employment Agreement (PPPK) and work in educational institutions with a non-fixed system of pay or based on teaching hours (Azzahra, S. 2023). Generally, honorary teacher receives a smaller fee compared to a PNS or PPPK teacher and does not enjoy the same number of rights and benefits as a teacher with PNS and PPPK status. However, various issues relating to the well-being and employment status of honourable teachers often become highlights that affect the quality of education and the continuity of their profession. (Prihutami, R. B., & Rahmiati, A. 2024).

The well-being of honorary teachers in Indonesia is often a public debate and highlight. Although they have the same contribution as teachers with PNS status, their rights and well-being are still far from ideal. This not only affects the motivation and performance of teachers, but also on the sustainability of this profession that potentially creates instability in education. (Kalsum, U., & Armela, S. 2023).

Increasing the well-being of honorary teachers in Indonesia is an urgent issue that cannot be negotiated anymore. Through a statement from Mendikbudristek, the government showed its seriousness in paying attention to the well-being of honourable teachers, including opening the opportunity for them to follow the selection of ASN PPPK in large numbers, i.e. up to 500 thousand formations (Yuliana et al., 2023). (Kulsum, U. 2023).

In addition, the improved well-being of honorary teachers was also stressed by Nadiem Makarim, Minister of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology. He appreciated the role and sacrifice of Indonesian teachers, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, and expressed commitment to continuing to improve their well-being. It shows that improving the well-being of honorary teachers is not only a moral

responsibility of the government, but also an important investment in ensuring that the quality of education in Indonesia can stay awake. (Humaeroh, E. 2023).

A better well-being of honorary teachers will have a positive impact on their motivation and performance in teaching. Thus, improving the well-being of honorary teachers is necessary to ensure that every child in Indonesia has access to quality education and is led by dedicated and motivated teachers. (Kulsum, U. 2023).

The well-being of honorary teachers has a significant link to the sustainability of the teacher profession and the quality of education in Indonesia. Analysis of teacher welfare policies suggests that improving teacher well-being is one of the key efforts inining talented and competent teachers, which ultimately impacts on improving the quality of education. This is because the well-being of teachers directly affects the motivation of work, commitment to the profession, and their capacity in delivering quality learning to students (Permatasari, D. 2023). Furthermore, the relationship between the welfare of the teacher and the quality of education in Indonesia is also seen in the competence and dedication of the teachers as the key to quality education. (Permatasari, D. 2023). Prosperous teachers are more likely to invest their time and resources in professional development and improvement of teaching methods, which indirectly improve the quality of education received by students (Kanti et al., 2023). Meanwhile, the inadequate welfare of honorary teachers often constitutes an obstacle to the sustainability of the teacher profession because it reduces the motivation and interest to remain in the teaching profession. This situation can result in a high turnover of teachers, where experienced teachers are replaced by new teachers who may not be fully prepared or qualified, which in turn affects the overall quality of education. (Kanti et al., 2023; Kurniasih, S. R., & Hermawan, A. H. 2023).

Increasing the well-being of honorary teachers, therefore, is important not only for individual teachers but also for the education system as a whole. Improved well-being can encourage the retention of qualified teachers, which is essential for the sustainability of the profession and the sustainable improvement of the quality of education offered in Indonesia.

Starting from this issue, the research was initiated with the aim of understanding more deeply about the welfare conditions of honorary teachers, as well as the challenges and opportunities in realizing the sustainability of the profession.

RESEARCH METHOD

The method of literary research is an approach in research that focuses on the collection of data from literature or written sources relevant to the subject of research. (Reay, 2014; Graue, 2015). This method involves keyword search to find relevant literature. There are 7 methods performed in Literature Studies, one of which is searching for relevant keywords in various reliable sources (Sgier, 2012); (Noble & Smith, 2014).

In an academic or scientific context, a method of literary study carried out by a researcher by collecting, analysing, and presenting relevant information on a topic from a secondary text source. It involves activities related to methods of collection of library data, reading and recording, as well as managing research materials from various sources such as books, journals, and magazines that relate to problems and purposes of research. (Grbich, 2012; Bazeley, 2013).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Teacher Welfare Standards

A teacher is a man who has dedicated himself to teaching, educating, guiding, and training his disciples to understand the knowledge which he teaches. (Haddar et al., 2023). In a broader sense, a teacher is not only a formal teacher but can also be a figure embedded by his students, suggesting that the role of a teacher extends beyond merely the transmission of academic knowledge. (Tuhuteru et al., 2023).

The well-being of a teacher is the condition in which a teacher feels satisfied and well with his work. (Apriliani et al., 2023). It covers various aspects, including, but not limited to, fair wages, a safe and positive working environment, as well as opportunities for sustainable professional development. The need for the movement and support of the local government plays a major role in achieving this well-being. The well-being of teachers also affects the quality of education given to the students. (Murwaningsih, T., & Fauziah, M. 2023).

The measurement of the welfare of teachers in Indonesia continues to be a major concern of the government. Indonesian Minister of Education, Culture, Research and Technology, Nadiem Makarim, reaffirmed that the government is working to improve the well-being of teachers in Indonesia. These efforts include improving the quality and well-being of teachers for the advancement of education in Indonesia. (Putrawan, G. D., & Marmoah, S. 2024). In another context, the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia has allocated significant funds to improve the capacity and well-being of teachers, including an allocation of funds for non-PNS teachers that is increasing every year, reflecting a commitment to improving the well-Being of Teachers. (Murwaningsih, T., & Fauziah, M. 2023).

Teacher welfare standards are a set of rules and policies designed to ensure that teachers get their rights properly, which support both their professional and personal lives. While welfare standards may vary from one country to another, some important elements that are usually included in these standards include: 1) Income and Remuneration: Efforts to ensure that teacher salaries are sufficient to sustain a decent life. These include welfare benefits, such as health insurance, pension benefits, and housing benefits. 2) Professional Development Opportunities: Provides opportunities for teachers to develop their professional skills through further education, training, workshops, and other development activities. 3) Working environment: Take into account the physical and psychological conditions of the workplace, including safety and health at work, and create a favourable and positive working environment. 4) Working time and holidays: Establish reasonable working hours and provide sufficient rest and vacation time to ensure a balance between work and personal life. 5) Recognition and Appreciation: Recognizing and appreciating the achievements and contributions of teachers through the awarding of recognition, promotion, or other forms of acknowledgement as a form of appreciation for their hard work. 6) Legal protection: Provides guarantees of legal protection for teachers, including in the case of employment disputes, discriminatory treatment, or other legal issues related to their profession (Al Mighwar, M., & Nopaulita, T. A. 2023; Gobel et al., 2023).

In Indonesia, attention to the well-being of teachers has gradually increased, as reflected in the increase in the minimum salary standards for teachers and government efforts to improve teachers' access to professional development programmes. This effort is in line with the Law No. 14 of 2005 on Teachers and Lecturers, which

emphasizes the importance of improving the quality and well-being of teachers and lecturers as the key to improving quality of education. (Asmendri, A., & Haviz, M. 2023).

Status and Protection of Honourable Teachers

Honourable teachers are educators who are usually officially appointed by authorities to address the problem of a teacher shortage in an educational institution. They don't have the status of civil servants (PNS) and often spend a small part of their time at school. As honorary staff, honorary teachers receive non-fixed fees, depending on working hours, and are generally much less than the salary of PNS or PPPK (Government officials with employment agreements) teachers. (Hasibuan, I. M. 2024).

The status of an honorary teacher in Indonesia is currently undergoing a transitional process. According to some reports, the government plans to remove the status of an honorary worker from 2023. However, there are still hundreds of thousands of honorary teachers in the country who have not yet obtained their status. It affects honorary teachers who often receive unworthy salaries and have to work without a certain job status despite having served for dozens or even decades. However, there's good news for the teachers. The Minister of Education, Nadiem Makarim, in 2022 has announced that 320,000 honorary teachers will be appointed to government officials with employment agreements. (PPPK). But, even though these changes are seen as a profitable step, there are still many challenges to face and the help that honourable teachers need in order to completely change their status to the CPPK. (Zahri et al., 2023; Prihatin, E., & Hartini, N. 2023).

In order to protect the rights and interests of honorary teachers in Indonesia, there are a number of rules and policies that have been established by the government, among them: 1) Law No. 14 of 2005 on teachers and lecturers. Although it focuses on the teacher and lecturer of public officials, this law provides a legal basis for the appointment and protection of their rights also applies to honorary professors. 2) Law no. 5 of 2014 on State Civil Appliances. (ASN). Although not directly regulating honorary teachers, this law provides a legal basis for the appointment of honorary professors to government officials with a contract of employment. (PPPK). 3) Government Regulations (PP) No. 49 of 2018. This PP explains about the management and transition of honorary personnel to the PPPK. In article 7 of this PP, it is stated that honorary staff who have not met the requirements to become ASN can be appointed to PPPK in functional posts according to their qualifications. 4) Permenpan-RB No. 36 Year 2019. This regulation of the Minister of PAN-RRB specifically regulates the procedure and conditions for the appointment of the PPPK, in which honourable personnel can also participate. (Al Mighwar, M., & Nopaulita, T. A. 2023; Gobel et al., 2023).

Further protection for honorary teachers must be consistent with the policies of the respective districts, bearing in mind also the many honourable teachers appointed by the local government. It should be remembered that although there are some regulations in force, there are still many challenges and obstacles for honorary teachers to obtain the same protection and rights as PNS or PPPK teachers. Further efforts are needed to address this problem and improve the well-being of honorable teachers in Indonesia.

Teaching Profession as a Sustainable Career

The teaching profession is a very important and valuable field in society. The definition of the teacher profession according to the source of Kemdikbud, refers to individuals who have the expertise, dedication, and specific qualifications to educate, teach, guide, and direct students so that they can develop academically and socially. This profession is not just about transmitting knowledge, but also shaping character and giving inspiration to the younger generation. (Astuti & Supriyono, 2020).

A teacher is expected to have competence in various areas, including teaching expertise, good interpersonal skills, and a commitment to continuous learning and development. (Mahardika et al., 2023). Glints stressed that a teacher should be able to design an interesting lesson plan, which is not only educational but also nurtures the motivation and curiosity of students. It shows the complexity of a teacher's task that is not only limited to the transfer of knowledge, but also covers other supporting aspects such as counselling and mentoring. Being a teacher also requires patience and perseverance, given that they will be dealing with different characteristics of students that require different approaches. (Prihatin, E., & Hartini, N. 2023). It makes the teaching profession not only a job, but also a vocation of the soul that requires teachers to continue to sharpen their ability to manage the classroom and build positive relationships with students. (Hasibuan, I. M. 2024).

In addition, the Ministry of Education has opened up the opportunity for S1 graduates of all majors to become professional teachers through the Prejabatan Teacher Profession Education Program (PPG). It demonstrates an effort to improve the quality of education by providing a quality education for those who have a strong desire in the field of education but do not have a formal background in the area of education. (Simmie, G. M. 2023).

In the context of professionalism, being a professional teacher is required not only to have extensive academic knowledge, but also skills and professional attitudes. The teacher room emphasizes that the criteria for professional teachers include communication skills, adaptability to educational technology developments, and a high level of professional ethics. (Boylan et al., 2023).

The teaching profession is strongly linked to the concept of sustainable work, both in terms of education and social and economic development. In the context of sustained work, continuous efforts are required to create conditions that enable present and future generations to have the opportunity to learn, develop, and live in a healthy and stable environment. (Ibda et al., 2023).

There are several ways teaching professions are relevant to the concept of sustainable work: 1) Educating about Sustainability: Teachers play an important role in educating students about sustainability issues, including climate change, responsible use of resources, and social justice. They can integrate these concepts into curricula on a variety of subjects, not just on science or geography lessons, to cultivate students' awareness and competence in acting as agents of change. 2) Shaping Skills for a Sustainable Future: The teaching profession aims to help students develop the skills necessary for the economy of the future, which is expected to be greatly affected by the need for sustainability. These include problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and adaptation, which enable them to contribute to sustainable solutions. 3) Promoting Environmental Awareness: Teachers can inspire students to take part in more sustainable life practices, such as waste reduction, efficient energy use, and resource

conservation. Environmental education plays a strategic role in educating generations who are more environmentally conscious and caring. 4) Shaping Character and Leadership: Through character education and example action, teachers play an important role in shaping future leaders who will appreciate and strive for sustainable work. By introducing concepts of ethics and responsibility, teachers help students to develop values that will guide their actions in the future. 5) Supporting Sustainable Economic Development: By providing quality education that prepares students with the skills required in the labour market, teachers contribute to more sustainable economic development. Educated and skilled workforce is the key to innovation and a sustainably growing economy (Ibda et al., 2023; Simmie, G. M. 2023, Gobel et al. 2023).

In the context of globalization and global sustainability challenges, the teaching profession is becoming more relevant than ever. Teachers have a key role to play in preparing the younger generation to face and cope with them, ensuring that they are able to make a positive contribution to sustainable and equitable development for all.

Challenges in the Sustainability of the Professions of Honourable Teachers

Some factors that may hinder the well-being and sustainability of the professions of honorary teachers include inadequate recognition and legal protection, low wages, and a lack of social security. The government needs to design regulations that guarantee the employment status and the basic rights of honorary teachers, including social security and the right to leave. Besides, there is also the issue of insufficient welfare policy in improving the quality of education, which includes aspects of worthy compensation for attracting and retaining teachers with good talents and abilities. (Putrawan, G. D., & Marmoah, S. 2024).

The well-being of honorary teachers is often ignored seriously, which is reflected in the very low salary. For example, there are honourable teachers who only receive salaries of around Rs. 100,000 to Rs. 350,000 per month, this situation is one of the serious challenges facing honorary teachers and the education sector in general. Besides, this problem is also linked to the low education budget in some areas that affects the limitation of funds to pay honorary teachers properly. (Pugach, M. C. 2023; McBain et al., 2024).

Strategy to Improve Professional Welfare and Sustainability

There are several strategies and recommendations for improving the well-being and sustainability of the professions of Honourable Teachers: 1) Increase of the Honorable Teacher's Wage: The honorable teacher's salary should be raised to be equal to the salary of a State official teacher or at least receive a regional minimum wage. It aims to honor and motivate honorary teachers in educating the younger generation. 2) Employment Rights Protection: Policy that guarantees honorary teacher employment rights such as holiday benefits, employment and health benefits, and annual leave. 3) Providing a Special Path of Appointment: Making a special path of appointment of honorary teachers to PNS teachers can be one of the solutions for improving the status and well-being of honorable teachers. 5) Infrastructure Preparedness and Support: Provision of adequate facilities and infrastructure will also help honorary teachers in carrying out their teaching duties. This support may include access to technology and learning resources, as well as a safe and conducive working environment. 6) Implementation of National Educational Standards: National educational standards must be enforced to maintain the quality of honorary teachers as is the case with PNS

teachers. 7) Strengthening the role of the Teachers' Union: The Teacher's Union must be strengthened as a strategic partner in policy dialogue and negotiation. They can play a role in expressing aspirations and guaranteeing the rights of honorary teachers. 8) Increased Education Budget: To implement the above-mentioned strategies, increased education budget becomes crucial. The education budget must be allocated efficiently and effectively to support the improvement of the well-being and sustainability of the professions of honorary teachers (Parkhomenko, O., & Iarmosh, O. (2023; McBain et al., 2024; Rahman et al., 2023).

By implementing these policy strategies and recommendations, it is expected to improve the well-being and sustainability of the professions of honorary teachers in the future.

CONCLUSION

The well-being of honorary teachers in Indonesia has a long and complex path in the endeavour to the sustainability of the profession. Since the enactment of the Law No. 14 of 2005 on Teachers and Docents, there has been a new hope for improving the well-being of teachers, through the remuneration of the teacher profession. (TPG). It has relatively improved the well-being of teachers compared to before. However, when compared to other professions, the well-being of teachers, especially honorary professors, is still like "heaven and earth". This shows the great inequality of well-being still felt by the honourable teacher.

The welfare of honourable teachers is not only about fulfilling the right to a decent income, but also about ensuring the sustainability of professions that are still heavily dependent on government policies and local political dynamics in various regions. Honourable teachers often only receive salaries in the hundreds of thousands, far from being worthy of living.

Furthermore, efforts to resolve the problem of honorary teachers through the selection of government officials by employment agreement (PPPK) also demonstrate serious efforts by the government to improve the well-being and sustainability of the honorary teacher profession. However, this selection and selection process still leaves many challenges and requirements to be met by an honorary teacher.

In conclusion, although some efforts have been made to improve the well-being and sustainability of the professions of honorary teachers, the journey towards the expected achievement is still long and challenging. A more inclusive and comprehensive policy from the government is needed to ensure that the well-being of all teachers, including honourable professors, can be guaranteed and sustained in the future.

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